

SCHOOL PRINCIPALS' SUPPORT PRACTICES ON TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT, TEACHERS' COMMITMENT, AND PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

Raul B. Chua Jr., LPT, MAT, Ed.D.

Graduate School, Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13372738>

ABSTRACT

Teachers' professional development is essential in achieving the quality of education with the school principals playing a vital part to obtain a conducive environment for continuous teachers' professional growth. This study aimed to determine the school principals' support practices on the professional development of senior high school teachers and their relationship to teachers' commitment and performance during the school year 2023 – 2024 in the Division of Rizal which served as basis for developing professional development program. This study utilized the mixed method of research specifically sequential exploratory design. The data gathering instrument for the qualitative type was the semi-structured interview questions while the quantitative type used the survey questionnaire and the IPCRF documents. The respondents were 37 school principals and 225 teachers for the quantitative type and eight school principals and 14 teachers for the qualitative type. The qualitative data were transcribed, coded and analyzed using the thematic analysis. Meanwhile, the statistical tools used to treat the quantitative data were the percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Pearson r, and correlated t-test. Findings revealed that school principals provided informational, emotional, appraisal, and instrumental support. While principals felt satisfied with their support practices, teachers desired more instrumental support to enhance their professional growth. Both groups shared similar views on teachers' commitment levels. Teachers developed competencies aligned with the KRAs of the IPCRF. Although principals' support positively influenced teachers' commitment, it did not significantly impact their performance. Based on these findings, a professional development program was proposed to improve and sustain principals' support for teachers' professional development.

Keywords: *school principal support, teachers' professional development, teachers' commitment, teachers' performance, professional development program*

INTRODUCTION

In the United Nations Report in 2022, it was reiterated that education stands as a fundamental right for all Filipinos. This responsibility is embraced by the Department of Education (DepEd) in its mission to uphold and advance quality education which further stipulated that this pursuit of excellence in education is pivotal, equipping learners with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to fulfill their potential and contribute meaningfully to society. Recognizing the role of quality education, the UN also underscored its significance as a bedrock for sustainable development, enhancing lives and empowering individuals to address global challenges innovatively. Within this context, it focused on improving quality education within the educational framework.

Prior to the UN 2022 report, Siena (2019) mentioned that teachers are the center of educational activities, who serve as architects of the future generation. Their role, according to Siena, “transcends curriculum delivery, extending to cultivating essential skills, and attitudes which are important in navigating an evolving world filled with complexities”.

In the same view, Schleicher (2019) stated, “The quality of an education system can never exceed the quality of its teachers.” Schleicher also claimed that the teachers' professional development initiatives directly shape the caliber of educators, thus, resonating throughout the educational sphere and affecting students' overall learning achievements. The channels through which teachers' professional growth occur are diverse, encompassing workshops, seminars, collaborative learning communities, peer mentorship, action research, online courses, and advanced degrees. These avenues require dedicated institutional commitment, including time, resources, and support, fostering pedagogical evolution, innovation, and ultimately, augmented student accomplishments.

According to Bernadine (2019), teachers' professional development can be best understood as a systematic process that promotes competence and creativity across their professions. This is aligned with the principles outlined in DepEd Order No. 35, series 2016, which emphasizes its full support for the continuous professional development of teachers. This is firmly rooted in the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 and the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Law. Furthermore, this is in accordance with DepEd Order No. 42, series 2017, which pertains to the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST).

In 2018, Gonong cited one of the findings of the World Bank that a significant number of teachers expressed the need for additional opportunities for professional training and learning. However, Gonong remarked that the path to effective teacher professional development is beset with challenges. He cited hindrances such as constrained time due

to multiple responsibilities, limited access to training in remote areas and financial barriers preventing participation in workshops. Furthermore, Siena (2019) remarked that the cascading training approach in mass settings may dilute content and restrict opportunities for teachers to demonstrate their competencies. These challenges are compounded in the Philippine context, where the soaring number of teachers, lack of administrative support, and complexities in program completion hinder access to professional development. For example, conventional week-long seminars may prove inadequate to sufficiently equip teachers with new curriculum demands.

Teachers' professional development is essential in achieving the quality of education with the school principals playing a vital part in this process. School principals are instrumental in a conducive environment for continuous professional growth. Leithwood et al. (2021) mentioned that effective leadership by school principals involves a profound commitment to the teachers' professional development. This includes providing feedback and support, access to resources, and creating opportunities for professional learning. In addition, Mthanti and Msiza (2023) highlighted that school principals may support teachers to their professional development through motivations to engage, creating learning environment, informing opportunities, and allocating resources.

Teacher commitment involves being dedicated to the school, students' success, and teaching profession. High levels of commitment are often connected with greater performance and a willingness to engage in continuous professional development. In the same view, Medul (2022) underscored that through the provision of school principals' support, the level of teachers' commitment and performance is sustainable.

As observed by this researcher, teachers have limited opportunities in terms of professional development due to several factors like funding, access to training programs, subject or grade-level focus, administrative support, and prioritization of development. As mentioned by Magallanes (2022), one of the Philippine teachers' concerns is the lack of opportunities on professional development that may enable more collaborative activities among teachers. In another article, Morales (2023) mentioned about the unseen struggles of teachers in the Philippines, such as: a) obtaining appropriate training and growth opportunities; b) inadequate financing for professional development programs; and c) insufficient support from educational institutions. He commented that these impede their growth and capacity to give the finest education available.

In another view, one of the reasons why this researcher was challenged to conduct this study is the quality of professional development implemented in the schools. Tupas and Noderama (2020) revealed that majority of the teachers are not satisfied with their professional development program like the in-service trainings that are conducted due to limited time, irrelevant topics for teachers' effectiveness and efficiency, and lack of administrators' support. Relative to this, the researcher would like to determine if this scenario also occurs in the School Division of Rizal where he belongs.

Lastly, limited support on professional development was also observed by this researcher. Garcia and Weiss (2019) stated several supports from school principals that

need to be addressed such as: access to effective and high valued types of professional development, provision of much time and resources needed, intensifying mentoring and coaching experiences, establishment of learning communities, and increasing professional development opportunities.

To address these issues and to foster sustained commitment to professional development, a deeper exploration of the nexus between school principals' practices on teachers' professional development, commitment, and performance are imperative towards education quality. While previous research findings have touched on factors influencing teacher well-being, the specific role of principal practices on these aspects and in shaping commitment and performance still need to be further explored.

As a new principal in one of the DepEd schools in the Division of Rizal, the researcher believes that there is a need to determine the best practices of incumbent school principals to serve as a model for the new and other school principals to improve their teachers' professional growth and development thereby improving also their commitment and performance. From the good practices of the school principals, an innovative professional development program could be developed for the use of the school principals. If this is done, this study hopefully will be able to determine if this could improve the commitment and performance of the teachers, hence this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the school principals' support practices on the professional development of senior high school teachers and their relationship to teachers' commitment and performance during the school year 2023 – 2024 in the Division of Rizal which served as basis for developing professional development program.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the school principals' support practices on the professional development of teachers based on the results of the interview and focus group discussion with the senior high school principals and teachers?
2. What is the extent of the school principals' support practices on the teachers' professional development on the following categories as perceived by the school principals and the teacher respondents?
 - 2.1 Emotional
 - 2.2 Instrumental
 - 2.3 Informational
 - 2.4 Appraisal
3. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the school principals' support practices on the teachers' professional development on the aforementioned categories?
4. What is the level of the teachers' commitment as regards the following categories as perceived by the school principals and the teacher respondents?
 - 4.1 School

- 4.2 Students
 - 4.3 Teaching work
 - 4.4 Profession
 - 4.5 Body of knowledge, skills, and attitudes
5. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the level of teachers' commitment on the aforementioned categories?
6. What is the level of the teacher respondents' performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) results during the school year 2022 – 2023 on the following domains?
- 6.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
 - 6.2 Learning Environment & Diversity of Learners
 - 6.3 Curriculum and Planning
 - 6.4 Assessment and Reporting
 - 6.5 Personal Growth and Professional Development
7. Is there a significant relationship between the school principals' support practices on the professional development of teachers and the following variables?
- 7.1 Teachers' commitment
 - 7.2 Teachers' performance
8. Based on the results of the study, what professional development program could be developed and proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a mixed-method approach, specifically a sequential exploratory design. For the quantitative part, the respondents included 37 school principals and 225 teachers from public senior high schools in the Division of Rizal for the school year 2023–2024. For the qualitative part, eight school principals and 14 teachers were selected. The sample size was determined using Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error. Teachers were chosen through simple random sampling, while school principals were selected using purposive sampling.

The study utilized two sets of data gathering instruments, one set for the qualitative method and another set for the quantitative research. The questionnaire was validated by five school principals and five master teachers who were not part of the study. Part I of the survey questionnaires for the quantitative phase is on the extent of school principals' support practices on the professional development of senior high school teachers in the following aspects: emotional, instrumental, informational, and appraisal support. It consisted of 20 indicators, five for each type of support. It utilized the 4-point Likert rating scale choices that was arbitrarily set by the researcher. Part II of the research instrument was about the level of teachers' commitment based on the following domains: commitment to the school, students, teaching work, profession, and body of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The 4-point Likert rating scale that was arbitrary set by the researcher was also used. Another separate instrument was also used. This was the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) of the teachers for the school year 2022 - 2023

Data collection occurred in two phases. In the first phase, qualitative data was gathered through a structured interview process following the Initiate–Response–Follow-up (IRF) pattern with audio recording and note-taking. In the second phase, quantitative data was collected by administering survey questionnaires to respondents either in person or through Google Forms for those in more remote schools. The Google Forms link was distributed with the help of the school principal and their administrative staff, and the researcher personally retrieved the completed paper questionnaires.

The qualitative data were analyzed using the thematic analysis (Creswell, 2023) of the transcribed interviews. The transcribed and coded data were analyzed by identifying the patterns or themes using Tesch (1990) strategy. Meanwhile, the statistical tools used to treat the quantitative data were the percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Pearson r, and correlated t-test.

RESULTS

PHASE 1: FOR QUALITATIVE DATA

This phase of the study explored the school principals' support practices on the professional development of senior high school teachers. Five females and three male school principals participated in the interview while 12 females and two male teachers joined the focus group discussion.

Figure 1. Occurrence of Codes on the Four Types of Support on Teachers' Professional Development based on the Interviews

Figure 2. Occurrence of Codes on the Four Types of Support on the Teachers' Professional Development based on the FGD
PHASE 2: FOR QUANTITATIVE DATA

This phase of the study is the quantitative component of the Sequential Exploratory Strategy. It deals with the collection of data from the respondents after which the analysis of data followed.

Table 1

Summary of Respondents' Perceptions on the Extent of the School Principals' Support Practices on the Teachers' Professional Development

School Principals' Support Practices	Respondents			
	School Principals		Teachers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Emotional Support	3.65	VHE	3.30	VHE
b. Instrumental Support	3.65	VHE	3.23	HE
c. Informational Support	3.76	VHE	3.30	VHE
d. Appraisal Support	3.69	VHE	3.29	VHE
Grand Weighted Means	3.69	VHE	3.28	VHE

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.76 – 2.50 Low Extent (LE), 2.51 – 3.25 High Extent (HE), 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Extent (VHE).

Table 2

Summary of Test of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of School Principals' Support Practices on the Teachers' Professional Development

Domains	School Principals		Teachers		Computed z Value	Decision	Interpretation
	OWM	s	OWM	S			
a. Emotional support	3.65	0.43	3.30	0.69	3.06	Reject the Ho	Significant
b. Instrumental support	3.65	0.34	3.23	0.72	3.46	Reject the Ho	Significant
c. Informational support	3.76	0.34	3.30	0.74	3.67	Reject the Ho	Significant
d. Appraisal support	3.69	0.40	3.29	0.73	3.25	Reject the Ho	Significant

Note: $\alpha = 5\%$

Critical z Value = 1.96

Table 3

Summary of Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of the Teachers' Commitment on the Five Categories

Level of Teachers' Commitment	Respondents			
	School Principals		Teachers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Commitment to the School	3.67	VHL	3.59	VHL
b. Commitment to the Student	3.61	VHL	3.55	VHL
c. Commitment to the Teaching Work	3.66	VHL	3.58	VHL
d. Commitment to the Profession	3.63	VHL	3.55	VHL
e. Commitment to the Body of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes	3.58	VHL	3.58	VHL
Grand Weighted Means	3.63	VHL	3.57	VHL

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Level (VLL), 1.76 – 2.50 Low Level (LL), 2.51 – 3.25 High Level (HL), 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Level (VHL).

Table 4

Summary of Test of Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Teachers' Level of Commitment on the Five Categories

Domains	School Principals		Teachers		Computed z Value	Decision	Interpretation
	OWM	Sd	OWM	Sd			
a. Commitment to the School	3.67	0.41	3.59	0.42	1.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Commitment to the Student	3.61	0.38	3.55	0.40	0.83	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Commitment to the Teaching Work	3.66	0.43	3.61	0.52	0.66	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Commitment to the Profession	3.63	0.34	3.55	0.41	1.11	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Commitment to the Body of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Skills	3.58	0.45	3.58	0.41	0.06	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

Note: $\alpha = 5\%$

Critical z Value = 1.96

Table 5

Summary of the Level of the Teachers' Performance Based on the Results of their IPCRF during the School Year 2022 – 2023

Key Result Area (KRA)	OWM	VI
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.73	O
2. Learning Environment & Diversity of Learners	4.51	O
3. Curriculum and Planning	4.45	VS
4. Assessment and Reporting	4.39	VS
5. Personal Growth and Professional Development	4.31	VS
Grand Weighted Mean	4.48	VS

Note: 1.00 – 1.49 Poor (P), 1.50 – 2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 2.50 – 3.49 Satisfactory (S), 3.50 – 4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 4.50 – 5.00 Outstanding (O)

Table 6

Summary of Test of Significant Relationship between the School Principals' Support Practices on the Teachers' Professional Development as Regards Teachers' Commitment and Teachers' Performance

x	y	r	t _{comp} Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Principals' Support Practices on the Teachers' Professional Development	Teachers' Commitment	0.69	6.46	Reject the H ₀	Significant
	Teachers' Performance	0.13	1.71	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

Note: $\alpha = 5\%$

Critical Value = 1.97

Table 7

Joint Display of the Qualitative Analysis and Quantitative Results

QUALITATIVE THEMES	METAINFERENCES	QUANTITATIVE DATA
Theme 1: Emotional Support	<p>SHSP4: "Of course, moral support, encouraging them to continue their work that they are doing well and, of course to uplift themselves in terms of teaching and learning process."</p> <p>TP4: "When it comes to support, since I'm not fond of going to the office of the principal, for me, I cannot see and feel any support."</p>	<p>Overall Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.65 (VHE) Teachers: 3.30 (VHE)</p> <p>Indicator 2: The school principals address the emotional needs of the teachers regarding their professional growth. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.59 (VHE) Teachers: 3.25 (HE)</p> <p>Indicator 3: The school principals create an environment that fosters emotional support for teachers' professional development. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.62 (VHE) Teachers: 3.26 (VHE)</p>
Theme 2: Instrumental Support	<p>SHSP4: "Financial support. We need them. That's the most important, number one resource that we</p>	<p>Overall Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.65 (VHE) Teachers: 3.23 (HE)</p>

	<p><i>should have to give to our teachers.”</i></p> <p>TP4: <i>“Personally, I haven’t encountered an instance where they told me that they have financial assistance. But maybe for others. But for me, I haven’t experienced that.”</i></p>	<p>Indicator 3: The school principals provide school financial support for teachers to attend conferences, workshops, or pursue advanced degrees. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.57 (VHE) Teachers: 3.07 (HE)</p> <p>Indicator 4: The school principals allocate school budget for the professional development opportunities, workshops, and training programs to enhance teachers' skills. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.70 (VHE) Teachers: 3.13 (HE)</p>
<p>Theme 3: Informational Support</p>	<p>SHSP1: <i>“Ok, Mr. Chua. In our school, I extend my support to the teachers’ professional development by conducting In-Service Training.”</i></p> <p>TP7 <i>“May dalawa kaming INSET at iilan lang na LAC session pero kalimantan ay hindi masyadong quality.”</i></p>	<p>Overall Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.76 (VHE) Teachers: 3.30 (VHE)</p> <p>Indicator 4: The school principals facilitate collaborative platforms, such as discussion forums or online communities, where teachers can share information and insights about professional development opportunities. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.70 (VHE) Teachers: 3.23 (HE)</p>
<p>Theme 4: Appraisal Support</p>	<p>SHSP7: <i>“I am also providing constructive feedback on the technical assistance on their professional development.”</i></p> <p>TP9: <i>“Our school principal does the observation and critiquing, that's how she did the support for me.”</i></p>	<p>Overall Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.69 (VHE) Teachers: 3.29 (VHE)</p> <p>Indicator 3: The school principals use mechanisms to evaluate and provide constructive feedback to assist teachers’ professional development. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.73 (VHE) Teachers: 3.24 (HE)</p>

		<p>Indicator 4: The school principals use self-assessment as a starting point for goal-setting and professional development discussions. Average Weighted Mean School Principals: 3.62 (VHE) Teachers: 3.25 (HE)</p>
--	--	---

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.76 – 2.50 Low Extent (LE), 2.51 – 3.25 High Extent (HE), 3.26 – 4.00 Very High Extent (VHE).

DISCUSSION

School Principals’ Support Practices on the Professional Development of Teachers Based on the Result of the Interview and Focus Group Discussion of the Senior High School Principals and Teachers

From the qualitative data, it could be surmised that four types of support have emerged from the interview and focus group discussion session with the school principal and teacher participants. These are informational, emotional, appraisal, and instrumental support as evidenced by the number of codes for each type of support shown in figure 1 and 2.

Figure 1 gives a clear view of the occurrence of the four types of support extended by the school principal participants on the professional development of the teachers. The bar graph shows that the school principals’ biggest support on the teachers’ professional development was informational, followed by emotional, appraisal, and instrumental. Meanwhile, figure 2 displays the occurrence of codes on the four types of support on the teachers’ professional development based on the FGD. The bar graph shows that the principals’ biggest support on the teachers’ professional development was informational, followed by instrumental, emotional, and appraisal.

From the results of the qualitative data, the data gathering instrument for the quantitative data was developed. Quantitative data were collected, presented, and interpreted.

Extent of the School Principals’ Support Practices on the Teachers’ Professional Development as Perceived by the School Principal and the Teacher Respondents

Based on the quantitative data collected, table 1 show that the school principals and the teacher respondents perceived the extent of their support practices on the teachers’ professional development as Very High as evidenced by the grand weighted means of 3.69 and 3.28, respectively. However, the teacher respondents perceived the extent of school principals’ instrumental support on professional development as High Extent only as evidenced by overall weighted mean of 3.23. These findings implies that as regards

the extent of support practices by the school principals on the teachers' professional development, school principals are satisfied with the aspects presented while teachers seek more instrumental support from the principals to enhance their professional aspect.

Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of School Principals' Support Practices on the Four Aspects of Teachers' Professional Development

Table 2 presents the summary of the test of significant difference in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of the school principals' support practices on the teachers' professional development on the four categories. The findings of the study showed that the perceptions of the school principals and teachers differ significantly on the extent of the school principals' support practices on the teachers' professional development in terms of emotional, instrumental, informational, and appraisal which are above the critical z value of 1.96 at 5% level of significance. This means that the respondents' perceptions are not the same in all the four categories. The perceptions of the school principals and the teachers regarding the extent of support practices for teachers' professional development differ significantly. This indicates that there is a variation in how the school principals and the teachers view the support provided.

Level of the Teachers' Commitment According to School, Students, Teaching Work, Profession, and Body of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes as Perceived by the School Principals and the Teacher Respondents

Table 3 displays the summary of the respondents' perceptions on the level of the teachers' commitment as regards the five categories, namely: commitment to the school, to the student, to the teaching work, to the profession, and to the body of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The data in the summary table reveal that the school principals and teacher respondents perceived the level of the teachers' commitment as Very High with grand weighted means of 3.63 and 3.57, respectively. This indicates a strong dedication and loyalty among teachers towards their school, students, teaching work, profession, and the body of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. This finding implies that the teachers invest their time and effort doing their work, even beyond the basic requirements of their profession to ensure the success and well-being of their students. More so, the findings reflect the general qualities of a good teacher worth emulating by the members of the other professions. As the saying goes, "once a teacher, he will always be a teacher." A teacher is one who inspires, motivates, and instills love for learning that extends beyond the walls of the classroom.

Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Teachers' Level of Commitment to the School, Students, Teaching Work, Profession, and Body of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes

Presented in table 4 the summary of the test of significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the level of the teachers' commitment as regards the five categories, namely: commitment to the school, commitment to the

student, commitment to the teaching work, commitment to the profession, and commitment to the body of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The perceptions of the school principals and the teacher respondents on the level of the teachers' commitment did not show a significant difference. This is evidenced by the computed z values which are all lower than the critical z value of 1.96. Therefore, it indicates that both groups share similar perceptions across all five categories. This finding means that the school principals and the teachers know each other very well because they are both aware of how they manifest their love for work, for their students, their profession, and even the degree of updating themselves on the new trends in education.

Level of the Teachers' Performance Based on the Results of their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) during the School Year 2022 – 2023

The data in table 5 reflect that the level of the teachers' performance is Very Satisfactory as evidenced by the grand weighted mean of 4.48. However, KRA No. 1 and No. 2 both got an Outstanding rating as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.73 and 4.51, respectively. The three other variables, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, and Personal Growth and Professional Development were also rated as Very Satisfactory as shown by their respective overall weighted means of 4.45, 4.39, and 4.31. These Outstanding and Very satisfactory ratings are indications that the teachers are doing their responsibilities and duties very well according to the standards of teaching. The findings concur with the study of Bancifra (2022) which found out that the teachers are performing within the Very Satisfactory level based on the result of their IPCRF, which implies a strong indication that the teachers' performance exceeded expectations.

Significant Relationship between the Extent of School Principals' Support Practices on the Teachers' Professional Development and Teachers' Level of Commitment

Based on the data in Table 6, the computed t-value of 6.46 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.97 with 223 degrees of freedom at the 5% level of significance. This indicates a significant relationship between the extent of school principals' support practices for teachers' professional development and teachers' commitment. On the other hand, the test for the significant relationship between school principals' support practices for teachers' professional development and teachers' performance shows that the computed t-value of 1.71 is lower than the critical t-value of 1.97 with 223 degrees of freedom at the 5% level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the extent of school principals' support practices for teachers' professional development and teachers' performance. This implies that while the support provided by school principals for teachers' professional development can influence teachers' commitment, it does not necessarily affect their performance.

Analysis of the Qualitative Analysis and Quantitative Result

The data in table 7 presents a joint analysis of qualitative data derived from interviews and focus group discussions, compared with the results of the statistical analysis. The identified theme of instrumental support was integrated with aspect 2 of school principals' support for teachers' professional development, specifically indicators 3 and 4, yielding weighted means of 3.07 and 3.14, respectively. Additionally, the lack of connections between teachers, as perceived from school principals, emerged as the theme of emotional support, linked to indicator 2, rated as High Extent (HE) with a weighted mean of 3.25. Furthermore, the inadequacy of evaluation tools for goal setting and constructive feedback in teachers' professional development was identified as a theme connected to indicators 3 and 4 of Appraisal Support, with weighted means of 3.25 and 3.24, respectively. Moreover, facilitating collaborative platforms for professional development opportunities was integrated with informational support, emerging as a theme connected to indicator 4, with a weighted mean of 3.23. These findings underscore the importance of acknowledging teachers' professional development needs, providing tangible support mechanisms, addressing emotional needs, and fostering an environment conducive to emotional support for facilitating their growth and development. The results suggest a pressing need to develop an innovative teachers' professional program aimed at enhancing school principals' support for teachers' professional development.

The joint analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data provides valuable insights into the dynamics of school principal support for teachers' professional development. Qualitatively, themes such as instrumental support, emotional support, and appraisal support emerged, highlighting the multifaceted nature of support provided by school principals. Instrumental support, encompassing tangible resources and assistance, was identified as crucial, while emotional support and appraisal support underscored the importance of addressing teachers' emotional well-being and providing constructive feedback for growth. Quantitatively, statistical analysis further explained these themes by assigning weighted means to specific indicators within each theme. For instance, indicators related to informational support received relatively high weighted means, indicating a perceived adequacy of professional development opportunities such as INSET and Lac sessions provided by school principals. On the other hand, emotional support indicators revealed a gap between perceived and provided support, suggesting room for improvement in addressing teachers' emotional needs.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. Codes and themes can be identified from the transcribed quotes of the individual interviewees and focus group discussion participants on school principal support practices on teachers' professional development.
2. School principals extended their support for the professional development of teachers.
3. School principals and teachers have viewed differently the support provided for the teachers' professional development.
4. The school principals and teachers have a similar impression of the teachers' level of commitment.
5. The teachers have developed appropriate competencies in their roles based on the KRA's of the IPCRF.
6. The support provided by school principals for teachers' professional development could influence the teachers' commitment but not their performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the analysis, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The proposed Professional Development Program may be submitted to the Office of the School Superintendent of the Division of Rizal for comments and possible implementation.
2. The proposed Professional Development Program for the school principals should be presented by the researcher during the two-day seminar for the participants' comments.
3. Parallel studies using the mixed method may be conducted by other research enthusiasts to verify if similar results prevail.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the research, the researcher initially sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Rizal through a letter which was forwarded to her office through Electronic Core Application of Rizal Education System v. 1.0. (ECARES). After the request letter was approved by the SDS, the researcher was referred to the school principals for their appropriate action with utmost consideration and strict compliance to DepEd Order No. 9, s. 2005. The school principals assisted the researcher in administering and retrieving the survey questionnaire. The respondents were assured that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without consequence. No coercion was applied to compel the respondents to complete the survey questionnaire or participate in the interview. Confidentiality and

anonymity of the provided information were guaranteed, with respondents' names being optional to maintain anonymity. Proper referencing was employed to acknowledge all sources of information utilized in the study, including journals and research studies cited.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to Almighty God for the blessings, guidance, wisdom, and inspiration that made this dissertation possible. Special thanks to his family, particularly his mother, sisters, and brother, for their unwavering moral support throughout the study. Sincere appreciation is also due to the experts who generously contributed their time, effort, and expertise, providing invaluable inputs, constructive feedback, and suggestions that significantly enhanced this research. The researcher is grateful to the School Division Superintendent for supporting and approving the request to conduct this study. Acknowledgement is also due to all the Public School District Supervisors, Senior High School Principals, and Teachers of the Division of Rizal for their wholehearted support, cooperation, and generosity in facilitating the data gathering for this research. Finally, thanks to friends, classmates, and colleagues who contributed to the development of this study and to all those who inspired and motivated the researcher throughout this journey.

REFERENCES

- Bancifra, J.J., (2022). Supervisory Practices of Department Heads and Teachers' Performance: Towards A Proposed Enhancement Program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and Technology* / P- ISSN 2815 – 245X / E – ISSN 2815 – 2468 / Retrieved on April 23, 2024 from www.apjaet.com
- Bernadine, G.G. (2019). Challenges Faced by Educators in the Implementation of Continuing Professional Teacher Development (CPTD): Gauteng Province. *Teacher Education in the 21st Century*. Retrieved on April 23, 2024 from https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Challenges-Faced-by-Educators-in-the-Implementation-Bernadine/d3f1b3cbd2933b34210fdec8146a0e16_af179ea1
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sixth edition. Los Angeles, SAGE
- Department of Education (2017). *National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)*.
- Department of Education (2020). *National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH)*.
- Department of Education (2023). *Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System – Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers*.
- Garcia, E. and Weiss E. (2019). The role of early career supports, continuous professional development, and learning communities in the teacher shortage. The fifth report in 'The Perfect Storm in the Teacher Labor Market' series. *Economic Analysis and Research Network*. Retrieved on May 18, 2024 from <https://www.epi.org/publication/teacher-shortage-professional-development-and-learning-communities/>
- Gonong, G. O. (2018) *Addressing Teacher Professional Development Issues: Supporting Teacher Quality*. Retrieved on September 18, 2023 from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2018/07/EducSummitAddressingTeacherProfessionalDevelopmentIssues.Nov2_.pdf

- Republic Act 10912 or the Continuing Professional Development Law of 2016
- Leithwood, K. A. (2021). Review of Evidence about Equitable School Leadership. *Educ. Sci.* 2021, 11, 377. Retrieved on September 18, 2023
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11080377>
- Magallanes K, Chung JY and Lee S (2022) The Philippine Teachers Concerns on Educational Reform Using Concern Based Adoption Model. *Front. Educ.* 7:763991. doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.763991
- Medul, A. P., (2022). School Leadership Behaviors of School Heads in Relation to Teachers' Work Performance and Organizational Commitment in Selected Secondary Schools in the Philippines. *American Research Journal of Humanities & Social Science (ARJHSS)*, E-ISSN: 2378-702X, Volume-05, Issue-03, pp-29-35. Retrieved on May 18, 2024 from <https://www.arjhss.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/E532935.pdf>
- Morales, Mark Joel (2023). Practices, Challenges, and Perceived Impact of Professional Development Activities among Senior High School Teachers. figshare. Thesis. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24493708.v1>
- Mthanti, B. J., & Msiza, P. (2023). The roles of the school principals in the professional development of teachers for 21st century Education. *Cogent Education*, 10(2). retrieved on April 27, 2024 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2267934>
- Siena, J. A. (2019). Decentralization and Teacher Professional Development in a Large Education System, Quezon City: UP Center for Integrative and Development Studies. Page 3 through Training and Development in Ghana Education Service (A Case Study of Ebenezer Senior High School). *Journal of Human Resource Management*. Vol. 6, No. 1, 2018, pp. 1-8. Retrieved on April 23, 2024 from doi: 10.11648/j.jhrm.20180601.11
- Schleicher, A. (2019). Thoughts on the Future of Teaching. *Beijing International Review of Education*, 1(2-3), 273-302. <https://doi.org/10.1163/25902539-00102002>
- Tesch, R. (1990). *Qualitative Research: Analysis Types & Software Tools*. Bristol, PA: Falmer Press.
- Tupas, F. P. and Noderama, R. P. (2020). Looking into In-Service Training for Teachers in the Philippines: Are They Gearing towards Education 4.0?. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(10), 4651 - 4660. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2020.081034.
- UNESCO (2021). Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Retrieved on November 3, 2023 from <https://tcg.uis.unesco.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2021/02/Metadata-4.c.7.pdf>